

Beyond The Surface: A Parental Examination of Elementary Students' Social Media Usage

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Abstract. This qualitative phenomenological study investigates the perspectives of parents regarding their children's engagement with social media, particularly its academic and personal implications. The study aims to explore the lived experiences of elementary-grade students on social media, the coping mechanisms employed by their parents, and the insights derived from these experiences. Ten parents of students from the Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy participated in in-depth, semi-structured interviews, serving as the primary research instrument. The research problem addresses growing concerns over the risks of early and unmonitored social media exposure, including behavioral imitation, emotional vulnerability, academic decline, and online safety threats. Using Colaizzi's method for data analysis, three major themes emerged: imitation of inappropriate digital content, emotional and cognitive effects of online validation, and concealed dangers such as cyberbullying and digital addiction. The findings revealed that parents actively navigate these challenges through digital restrictions, open communication, and value-driven interventions. The study concludes that while social media presents both opportunities and threats, increased parental awareness and strategic mediation are vital to safeguarding children's well-being. These insights contribute to the development of responsible digital practices and inform educational policy and future research.

KEY WORDS

1. Elementary learners 2. parents 3. social media 4. technology

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1. Introduction

Social media platforms have evolved into expansive cyberspaces for connecting, creating, and navigating real-time scenarios. With just one click, a lot can happen. This poses a dilemma for younger users who are increasingly exposed to social media interactions. The pervasive negative factors affecting elementary school learners on these platforms continue to impact their academic and personal experiences, particularly concerning their age-appropriate development as digital citizens. Due to the globalization of communication and the post-pandemic surge in using various social media platforms for education across different subject areas, learners are utilizing social media at an unprecedented rate. Social media has significantly expanded opportunities for students to share their thoughts and feelings. However, its social support system may not meet its emotional requirements, or its purported benefits might not last long (Chen Xiao, 2022). Ahmad and Murad (2020) suggested that social media has become essential for communicating and exchanging knowledge during the pandemic,

when interaction with others and social distancing were limited. Being told to stay home has led many people to turn to social media for entertainment and social connections. On a global scale, Abaido (2020) proposed that online technology is the primary means of modern communication nowadays, which may encourage negative or hazardous behaviors. For instance, cyberbullying is a notable instance of such detrimental or destructive behavior. He added that despite the convenience of using online technologies, continuous exposure to and contact with them exposed individuals to specific internet connections that could jeopardize their safety and mental and emotional health. Likewise, in the United States, there seems to be an increase in skulking activity on social networking sites. Furthermore, the frequency and rate at which people use social media news websites were rising. With the sheer volume of individuals using social media and how simple it is to create an account, this is concerning since it makes it much simpler for people to become victims of online fraud. One issue linked to frequent social media usage is distinguishing between reliable and unreliable data (Hruska Maresova, 2020). As a rampant case in Pakistan, Awan and Kauser (2019) revealed that due to their apparent infatuation with the captivating realm of social media, some worried parents have voiced their grave concerns that they are finding it challenging to capture their kids and wards' attention. Some young people have created a fantasy and illusion-based world, isolating themselves from reality. If the risky social media network "obsession" tendency is allowed to continue, it may worsen Pakistan's already failing educational system. It may be plausible to suggest that today's students are underperforming in the classroom. In the national scene of the Philippines, Antone (2022), cited in the study of Gonzales (2019), stated that cyberbullying, as a common effect of social media, continues despite the legislation passed in 2013.

Twenty-two incidents of cyberbullying were reported to the Philippine National Police between 2017 and March 2019. According to the PNP's records, most of the victims were kids, and all the incidents occurred at schools. Therefore, cyberbullying is one of the most harmful effects of the improper use of social networking sites. In Cagayan Valley, Chu and Luyun (2019) observed that several parents believe that social media negatively impacts students' academic performance, which is still aligned with the Philippines' conservatism trait that misled the concept of social media usage. However, other parents believe that allowing their kids to use social media will make them more aware, intelligent, and successful in school. Similarly, Cruz et al. (2022) supported that, for instance, in the political aspect, Filipino youth have such involvement in giving online feedback when it comes to political issues, even with their lack of understanding of governmental systems, their poor attitude toward voting responsibly, and their meager social involvement, all of which continue to be problems. Only a few decided not to participate because they thought it would affect their academic performance. On the other hand, Raganta et al. (2021) conducted a survey at a National High School in Nueva Ecija about the adverse effects of social media. The survey revealed that both men and women students acknowledged that online activity makes them reliant on technology, particularly search engines, to complete their schoolwork. Furthermore, all the respondents agreed they needed more time to review their courses due to social media use. They also stated they had less time for in-person conversations with their parents and loved ones. Locally, Mangarin and Montañó (2021) revealed in the study they conducted within the locality of Davao City that online platforms can be used for a variety of harmful purposes, such as online harassment, sexual exploitation of fellow students, and even cyberbullying. Also, 50 % of the students use

the internet for longer every day. Whereas 22.7 % consumed monthly and 64 % experienced cyberbullying. The study presents prevailing detriments concerning social media's negative impact, specifically on elementary grade-level learners. It is also in this context that I have decided to conduct this study, as students also use social media as part of their academic endeavors. Nonetheless, this study examines grade-level students' risks of using social media in personal and academic aspects through the lens of their parents. Fortunately, this study is valuable in further developing an in-depth undertaking related to previously conducted studies.

- (1) What are parents' perspectives on the online experiences of their elementary-grade children through the use of social media or cyberspace?
- (2) What coping mechanisms do parents employ for their children's social media usage and risks?
- (3) What insights can be gained based on the results?

The findings of this research provide significant benefits to the following grantees: Educational Sectors The data acquired for this study will be critical in the global education arena for pursuing this issue, and it may also offer additional resources for developing solutions. School heads The study's conclusion will help institutions devise fresh concepts to dispel rumors about social media's potential risks to academic and personal lives. Additionally, using this study as a foundation, they can heighten another connected investigation. Educators The insights gained from this study will enhance teachers' experience with social media use. However, they may need to develop plans to reduce social media overuse. Parents The study findings will be used to empower and educate parents on how social media shapes their children's academic growth and personal development. Students The research's findings may also benefit students' awareness of social media and its limitations, which might impact their learning. Future Researchers This study will provide a

1.1. Purpose of the Study—This qualitative phenomenological study investigates parental perspectives on their children's social media utilization for academic and personal purposes. It seeks to identify solutions that will be extracted from the parents' viewpoints of their children's social media usage.

1.2. Research Questions—This study examines the hidden dangers of social media in the experiences of the elementary grade level students of the Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy. Primarily, it seeks to answer the following inquiries:

vital core data collection to enhance the current research and conduct new studies. Future researchers could find answers or more sources to expand on this research. Similarly, the information supplied would inspire further research on this subject for advocates.

1.3. Review of Significant Literature—

1.3.1. Social Media Usage by Students—Social media aims to connect people globally and has become vital for communication, knowledge exchange, and entertainment, especially during crises (Ahmad Murad, 2020; Aichner et al., 2021). Teachers recognize its educational potential but struggle to balance its benefits with distractions, often due to limited technical-pedagogical skills (Thurlings et al., 2020).

However, excessive use is linked to mental health issues, negative social comparisons, cyberbullying, sleep deprivation, and poor academic performance (Braghieri et al., 2022; Abi-Jaoude, 2020; Kolhar et al., 2021; Agostiniani et al., 2022). Risks include early sexual ac-

tivity, exposure to inappropriate content, and digital footprint concerns. Specific issues are cyberbullying (Giumetti Kowalski, 2022), sexting (Chitra, 2021), and “Facebook depression” from online isolation (Yoon et al., 2019; Miller, 2020).

Overexposure may also harm literacy, health, and physical activity levels, leading to obesity or behavioral issues (Awaliyah et al., 2021; Ikems et al., 2023). Social media affects body image (Blair et al., 2020; De Vries et al., 2019) and encourages self-presentation pressures (Grealish et al., 2020; Noori et al., 2023). It also exposes youth to rapid technological changes that challenge cultural norms (Qudaisat, 2023; Yousefi Zangeneh, 2023). Younger users face stronger negative impacts (Lin Lachman, 2020).

1.3.2. Parental Actions Addressing Risks—Parents employ strategies such as control (screen limits), discussion, engagement in alternative activities, and trust-building to guide children’s responsible social media use (Milivojević et al., 2018; Abdelmoneium, 2023). Awareness programs and school-based activities can strengthen responsible use (Kaban, 2021). Effective mediation includes open communication, monitoring tools, and expert support (Helfrich et al., 2020; Kim Lou, 2019). Privacy management is encouraged through active mediation (Kang et al., 2022).

Younger victims of online abuse often respond passively, such as blocking bullies (Myers Cowie, 2019). Early media exposure can enhance literacy but also heighten risks (Guerero Forment, 2019). Internet addiction can cause social isolation and reduced well-being (Akinci et al., 2024; Meshi Ellithorpe, 2021). Post-pandemic, excessive online engagement may hinder offline reintegration (Boursier et al., 2020).

1.3.3. Balancing Benefits and Risks—While social media can enhance creativity, social skills, and educational outcomes when used

purposefully (Tartari et al., 2019), misuse leads to fatigue, withdrawal, and mental health decline (Dhir et al., 2018; Allcott, 2020). Recommended measures include restricting harmful sites, developing educational apps, and integrating student-centered learning strategies (Ansari et al., 2020). Educators can leverage platforms like Instagram and YouTube to support learning goals (Armansyah Munastiwi, 2021).

1.4. Synthesis—Various studies across countries have emerged on the issue of social media and its impact on the academic participation of elementary-level students from the perspective of their parents. Since social media encompasses the worldwide arena, internet users can leave behind traces of the websites they have visited when they visit different websites. One of the biggest concerns for adolescents on online social networking sites is their digital footprint and future reputations, commonly online harassment, cyberbullying, and sexting, to name a few (Agostiniani, 2022). Parents perceived that internet use has a pessimistic influence on elementary school students, rather than being viewed as an optimistic usage (Benedetto Ingrassia, 2021). However, actions were taken to address the hidden dangers of social media. For some parents, establishing open and healthy communication while monitoring their technical usage will help them to manage the addiction and possible influences brought by social media to their young children (Helfrich et al., 2020). Moreover, seeking the assistance of an expert was to extend the necessary support for the children.

1.5. Theoretical Lens—This research is grounded in Mishra and Koehler’s (2006) idea of Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. This theory combines pedagogical knowledge (PK), content knowledge (CK), and technological knowledge (TK), which are the three main areas of expertise for teachers. Kurt (2019) emphasizes the importance of understanding the interconnections between these components and

their interplay to facilitate effective technology-based instruction. Elementary school students' involvement with technology is essential as it advances their acquisition of new knowledge, particularly information circulating on social media. This theory can be utilized to determine how social media's negative and positive aspects affect their personal and academic experiences. Consequently, this study was grounded in Cialdini's (1993) theory of informational social influence, which posits that we imitate other individuals when unsure about how to act appropriately. As a result, we look to them for guidance on appropriate behavior since we believe they are competent. This is a safe course of action because, at the very least, we are very concerned about what other people think of us. At worst, they cannot blame us for what we have done. Essentially, this study drew on the sociocultural theory of cognitive development (Vygotsky, 1978), in which Vygotsky emphasizes that at every learning milestone of younger students, there is a knowledgeable other who guides them throughout the process, which is necessary for molding learners' curiosity towards the application of social media platforms. The above theory can be applied to investigate the influences brought about by social media and how it affects the well-being of learners and educators. Understanding must act not just through

words. Elementary school learners need further guidance and parental involvement, rather than simply letting them become addicted to social media trends or issues. They need educational support and other learning opportunities. Primarily, this study draws on two key theories to explore how individuals navigate social media and how these virtual platforms impact their academic performance. First and foremost, the theory of Mishra and Koehler (2006), known as TPACK or Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge, suggests the application of technology in teaching and how technical advancements have made research more efficient and effective. Primarily, Cialdini's (1993) theory of social information suggests that any interaction can have a significant impact on learning acquisition, particularly among young learners in this generation who are tech-savvy and somewhat prone to online skepticism. Based on Figure 1, this research conceptualizes the experiences and challenges faced by elementary school students regarding the hidden dangers of social media as they navigate their personal and academic endeavors. Thus, information is based upon the observation and viewpoints of their parents. Additionally, the parents' coping mechanisms that they had to utilize and the insights gained throughout the process will serve as the basis for other proponents to extend such a phenomenon.

2. Methodology

This chapter includes an overview of the procedures and methods utilized in phenomenological research, which systematically investigates the research's aim and conclusions. Additionally, this research presents the research participants, research design, detailed data collected and analyzed, and other approaches, including ethical considerations throughout the study.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The inquiry of a study was guided by its philosophical foundations and qualitative presumptions. The theoretical underpinnings of the conceptual framework for qualitative research include ontological, epistemological, axiological, and

methodological assumptions. Understanding philosophical presuppositions is crucial for maintaining consistency between the study objectives, methodology, and findings interpretation, according to Kivunja and Kuyini (2020). As their work demonstrates, the researcher's

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

philosophical position shapes the design, including the techniques for gathering and analyzing data, and ultimately shapes the process of knowledge production. Therefore, the philosophical assumptions are as follows: Ontology According to Scotland (2020), ontology is the study of the researcher’s views of the form and nature of reality, whether it is subjective and multifaceted or objective and single. Ontological presuppositions in qualitative research often align with the idea that reality is socially constructed and shaped by personal experiences and environments. As a proponent of this study, to increase my understanding of the nature of the research participants’ experiences, I will personally interact with them through in-depth interviews. Through this, they can serve as a primary source of information that will make conducting this research firm and possible. Epistemology Mohajan (2020) claims that interpretivist epistemology, which emphasizes the joint knowledge building of researchers and participants, is typical of qualitative research. This presumption encourages subjective and interactive research as opposed to remote observation. This assumption enables me to gather, validate, and inter-

pret data from human experiences. Additionally, through this assumption, the acquired methods and instruments were used to gain a comprehensive understanding of the lived experiences of research participants. Axiology In qualitative research, as explained by Alase (2021), axiology recognizes the impact of the researcher’s ethical considerations and values at every stage of the investigation. Because cultural and personal values are inextricably linked to interpretation, qualitative researchers do not aim for value-free inquiry. This was significant because such values influence the research methodology and its conclusions. Likewise, Yulianto (2021) suggests that values were the focus of axiology. To ensure a fair interpretation of results and that the overall findings strictly adhere to the ethical considerations in conducting research. Methodology According to Creswell and Poth (2021), methodology was the overarching plan that connects specific data-gathering and analysis techniques to philosophical assumptions. Methodologies such as ethnography, grounded theory, and phenomenology in qualitative research are based on interpretivist assumptions. An effective research process further enhances the valid-

ity and dependability of the research outcomes (Sreekumar, 2023). I will define, evaluate, and justify the use of research techniques, such as a qualitative phenomenological study with research interviews and theme analysis, to achieve the desired results. Rhetoric As Given (2020) outlines, qualitative rhetoric tends to be informal, personal, and expressive of the researcher's voice, often written in the first person to emphasize transparency and engagement with participants. Thus, the term encompasses the use of language, communication competencies, and conveying strategies to persuade readers' perceptions of the subject matter of the research. To ensure that the data were made available to the readers' perspectives and knowledge, and that the information written is informative and persuasive in the same manner.

2.2. *Qualitative Assumptions*—The phenomenological research design employed in this study adopts an approach that seeks to determine and explore the lived experiences of elementary students in encountering the hidden dangers posed by social media at Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy. To assume that people's distinct viewpoints give meaning to what they see, and that reality is socially produced. Because they value lived experiences, they collect rich, culturally embedded data using techniques such as in-depth interviews and observations. The essential beliefs of phenomenological research are consistent with the idea that people actively create their realities and that personal experiences provide critical new perspectives on the subject under study. Moreover, I shall recognize the different perspectives and other beliefs that may influence elementary students' understanding of the hidden dangers of social media.

2.3. *Design and Procedure*—To customize the optimal research design, data collection strategy, and data analysis approach based on the study's objectives, it was crucial to specify the precise approach to be taken. A qualitative

research design will be used in this investigation. Hammersley (2023) states that studies emphasizing verbal analysis over statistical analysis are a good fit for qualitative research. The most appropriate design was qualitative, as it examined elementary students' lived experiences of social media usage, parents' coping strategies, and parents' insights into the hidden dangers of social media in their personal and academic undertakings. To prove or disprove any hypothesis by describing and elaborating on this phenomenon. Qualitative research encompasses a range of methodologies, including case studies, phenomenology, ethnography, grounded theory, and narrative research. I will employ a transcendental qualitative phenomenological study design to better understand the lived experiences of the subjects mentioned above. According to Cropley (2019), each person creates their own independent, unique understanding of the universe by considering their relationships with other individuals and the external world. Mohajan (2020) argues that rather than being based on unchangeable facts, what people—including academics—accept as true is often influenced by their subjective experiences, perceptions, and social settings. By seeking a deeper understanding of human behavior and life experiences, qualitative research welcomes this subjectivity and produces knowledge that is both contextually rich and useful. According to Husserl, as cited in Kaufer and Chemero's book (2021), phenomenology is described as an organized study of a significant part of human experience. In this sense, significant experiences are ultimately shaped by the experiences people undergo throughout their lives. Meanwhile, transcendental learning involved examining various perspectives and maintaining an open mind, leading to the creation of new knowledge based on the relevance of experiences. Therefore, this study aimed to explore the experiences of elementary students regarding the hidden dangers of social media and their parents' coping mech-

anisms and insights into this phenomenon.

2.4. Ethical Considerations—According to Arifin (2018), any research data must ensure the safety of human subjects by adhering to appropriate ethical guidelines. Respective research proponents then adhered to the ethical standards and directives of qualitative research. The regulations that follow are briefly explained. Social value Although the term "social value" lacks a single, universally accepted definition, it can be argued to encompass a broader range of non-financial effects of initiatives, organizations, and interventions, including environmental impact, social capital, and the welfare of individuals and communities. This concerns the immense advantages brought by the research to society. Thereby, a solution to address the daily detriment of individuals. To carefully weigh the study's potential influence and significance for the broader community while evaluating its societal value. By accomplishing this, it is ensured that funding is going toward studies that could benefit society tremendously. Informed consent For studies involving human subjects, informed consent is a moral and legal necessity. To make an informed decision, a participant must be fully informed about every facet of the trial. Once this is done, the person was willing to engage in a research field. In this sense, I will consider participants' paramount privacy, allowing them to decide whether to accept the opportunity to participate as an informant in the research study, thereby ensuring its full acceptance. Vulnerability In research, vulnerable studies are those that are more likely to be harmed, exploited, or subjected to coercion because of characteristics such as age, mental capacity, financial background, or physical health issues. The term means the incapacity to avert danger or act in the event of a calamity. In this manner, I will take the necessary precautions to protect potential participants and acknowledge and consider their potential susceptibility. This required modifying study procedures to

minimize negative impacts or implementing additional safeguards and support. Risks, benefits, and safety These components are necessary to assess the advantages and disadvantages of research participation and to implement safety precautions for participants. These elements in the research context entail evaluating the possible benefits and drawbacks of study participation and developing plans to guarantee participants' well-being. In this research, I carefully weighed and analyzed these key concepts to recognized the hazard within a particular location while ensuring the utmost safety of the research participants. Privacy and confidentiality While they are legally distinct concepts, confidentiality and privacy are often employed synonymously. Ethics forbids some people from disclosing information to outside parties, known as confidentiality. The freedom from having personal information or concerns invaded is known as privacy. When sending authorization before formally gathering data through online surveys and interviews in the investigation, it is essential to consider and respect the participant's decision and rights, particularly for their safety, if they decide to withdraw from the study at any point. The respondent's right to privacy and anonymity must be respected. Justice The duty to treat individuals fairly and equally was referenced in this idea. This involved considering issues such as preventing bias when drawing samples from a larger community and avoiding procedures that might put participants at a disadvantage during the study. In this study, I will ensure that vulnerable groups are not exploited or excluded from their studies. Furthermore, it adheres profoundly to the idea that everyone who potentially benefits from the research could receive its benefits. Throughout the research process, this method encouraged equity and justice.

2.5. Research Participants—Gathered information from selected parents of elementary-level students at Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy. The number of parents was limited to

approximately ten to fifteen. To ensure the quality and depth of interview data, the careful selection of participants and the use of follow-up interviews were essential in clarifying and enriching the participants' responses throughout the study. As Creswell and Poth (2021) explained, qualitative research commonly involves a small number of participants—typically ranging from five to twenty-five—allowing researchers to explore individuals' lived experiences in depth. They emphasized that qualitative inquiry prioritizes understanding the meaning participants assign to their experiences and relies heavily on detailed narratives and reflective data collection. The participants being selected for the interview for this study are those qualified to meet the following criteria: (1) must be a parent of an elementary-level student of the mentioned institution or academy, preferably at level 2 up to 6; and (2) their children (elementary-level students) must have prior experience in social media sites and other virtual interactions. Nonetheless, the interview will be conducted exclusively for parents with elementary-level children. I firmly affirm that the parents of those elementary-level students are eligible to express their opinions and viewpoints about the issue tackled in this research. Henceforth, they will stand on behalf of their minor-aged children. Since then, schools have not allowed elementary learners to participate in research. Thus, parents or guardians can testify and express their awareness of the study.

2.6. Research Instrument—It is essential to realize that various techniques are used in qualitative-phenomenological research to collect data. As such, I placed a strong emphasis on conducting in-depth interviews (IDI) using semi-structured interviews. According to Berle and Magaldi (2020), semi-structured interviews are exploratory interviews most commonly used in the social sciences to collect data for qualitative research projects or clinical purposes. A semi-structured interview allows for exploration

and provides room to follow topical trajectories as the conversation progresses, even though it usually adheres to a predetermined guide or protocol that focuses on a core topic to provide a basic structure. Furthermore, because they can be adjusted in response to the respondent's comments and interactions, semi-structured interviews offer great flexibility. Topics and ideas emerge organically from the participatory dialogue fostered by these conversations, allowing for deep, qualitative insights into people's perceptions of the topic being studied.

2.7. Data Collection—For gathering data sources, the research acknowledges the following manner of conducting the study as an awareness of all individuals who may be participating in such in-depth investigations, per se: First and foremost, secured a research letter for endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School. This formal validation enabled me to conduct the research truthfully and properly, taking into account all relevant ethical considerations. This will take place in the first week of April 2024. After obtaining the recommendation, consult the school division superintendent. The research project and its significance to the academic community had to be described in a formal letter of comparable length. I will include Chapters 1 and 2 in the research instrument, detailing the study's goals and the participants' identification. After permission was granted, go to the heads of the schools in the chosen institutions for approval. Lastly, official request letters will be sent to each school head. The letters should explain the study's goal and the anticipated duration of data collection. Once the school leaders agree, the research participants provide consent. Used written consent forms that spell out the study's goals, participant freedoms, and anonymity procedures to accomplish this. After obtaining consent from each participant, I will arrange and conduct the interviews using a structured or partially structured interview guide to guarantee consistency

and dependability in data collection.

Data Coding and Thematic Content Analysis Ultimately, to perform theme content analysis and data coding. This involves carefully reviewing the transcribed material and categorizing it methodically into themes, subcategories, and categories based on the interviewees' answers. By identifying patterns and connections in the data, we can conclude and gain insights that address the study's objectives.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—Examining phenomenological data involved several crucial steps. Colaizzi (1978) proposed seven processes for data analysis: familiarization, identification of significant statements, meaning-making, theme grouping, creation of a detailed description, provision of the central framework, and validation. Following multiple readings of the participant's remarks, a consensus was reached on the portion of the created questionnaires or data that should be used for familiarization purposes. Proceed to the second phase, locating notable statements. In contrast, this strategy focused on connecting phrases and sentences that will be discussed and directly related to the analysis, and extracted and created the main concepts from the interviewees' comments using this method. By contrast, participants in the third strategy, dubbed "constructing meanings," had to create meanings before they could read their central claims. Examining the new ideas that emerge from the data is vital throughout this process. As a result, adjusted the created meanings and confirmed the quality of the question formulations to ensure credibility and accuracy during the data-gathering process. The next stage in the clustering procedure was assembling the defined meanings that frequently appear in all participant testimonies. Used this approach to ensure the stated themes align and stress consistency throughout the analytical step. Another aspect of the fifth phase was creating a comprehensive description that includes all relevant details about the phenomenon under study,

verifying that any modifications were made in response to participant input, and ensuring that the underlying structure of the phenomenon aligns with the participants' perceived relevance. Forming the fundamental framework was another task for the sixth step. After a lengthy description is compressed into a succinct and dense declaration of the participants, only those considered crucial to the phenomenon's structure will be recorded. Verification, the last stage, will only be possible if I complete the data collection or obtain accurate data. This phase will involve evaluating and validating the emerging concepts from the data. I will ensure that the questions are worded precisely during the data collection to obtain trustworthy results, if not conclusions.

2.9. *Analytical Framework*—In phenomenological research, the analytical framework pertains to a methodical and organized approach to interpreting, analyzing, and displaying data. Colaizzi's method was employed to analyze the data collected from participant interviews and conversations about their experiences participating in extracurricular activities for this research project. As stated by Morrow et al. (2021), Colaizzi's (1978) approach has a unique seven-step procedure that provides a thorough analysis while closely following the data at every turn. With the participants' validation, this approach yields a concise yet thorough account of the phenomenon being studied. Extensive firsthand narratives of experiences are necessary for this method to be effective, and they can be gathered in several ways. The primary goal of framework analysis is to identify, characterize, and interpret meaningful patterns in cases and across themes related to the subject under study. Data Familiarization Acquired a comprehensive understanding of the topic under investigation by thoroughly interpreting the transcripts and going over them multiple times. For a more in-depth examination of the participants' experiences, a thorough review process is necessary to

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

understand the nuances of their claims. Identifying Significant Statements Every remark in the tales directly relevant to my research topic was meticulously identified. A detailed analysis of the collected data—such as written accounts or transcripts of interviews—must be conducted to

pinpoint and highlight the specific experiences that were the subject of the study. This is crucial in ensuring my analysis remains on topic and serves as a strong foundation for further subject development.

3. Results and Discussion

This study presents the information gathered from parents’ responses, informed by the research questions. These participants shared their encounters, coping strategies, and insights regarding their elementary learners’ social media usage.

3.1. The experiences of elementary grade-level school parents’ towards their children’s social media platform usage —Social media has taken center stage in today’s technologically advanced society, especially for elementary school-aged learners. With younger audiences having greater access to online plat-

forms, parents face a challenging terrain of technology use, safety issues, developmental effects, and shifting social norms. Likewise, it shed light on the challenges faced by parents of elementary-level students from Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy. Parents who must monitor and supervise their children’s online ac-

tivities face numerous challenges, despite these platforms offering opportunities for creativity, education, and connection. The emotional and developmental impacts of early exposure to digital interactions, age-appropriate content, screen time limits, cyberbullying, and online safety are issues that many parents struggle with. As kids are increasingly influenced by digital culture, challenges arise in establishing limits, staying current with evolving technology, and fostering genuine interaction.

3.1.1. Consequences through imitation— Through our behavioral actions, younger generations will essentially adopt the good attitude as well. Similarly, the Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy ensured a valuable learning environment in which they model a good role and a responsible way of acquisition. However, due to the wide range of social media platforms, children can access them freely without adequate safety precautions. Additionally, it somehow manipulated their minds to follow or emulate anything, regardless of the content shown on any social media platform. Among the aforementioned statements of the participants, they shared similar concerns specifically about their children's imitative behavior. From the response of Parent 1, he mentioned that his child had visually copied a viral video containing malicious or mature actions, which certainly captivated the child's attention. Indeed, it is not new today how kids are likely to emulate whatever catchy content appears on social media sites, including TikTok, which has become the most visited platform for all ages. With its features, namely short videos, creative skits, and trending details, children will quickly adopt the idea presented through it, and boredom will have no place after all. On the other hand, parent 2 stated the downside of letting your kid play online games along with users from different places. Without restrictions, they can navigate vulgar words and phrases that can leave a mark on their minds. Aside from that, there are gaming websites that

require individual users to complete some fields before having an account, particularly for those of legal age and above, which means those below the legal age are excluded from joining. Additionally, Parent 6 stated that pranking videos made her child emulate the same behavior. Nowadays, millions of viewers are invested in video influencers who upload content primarily featuring pranks in public spaces or real-time events. This will easily capture the attention of elementary-grade-level students, as most of them own a mobile phone. This finding was consistent with the informational social influence theory proposed by Cialdini (1993), which posits that people often adopt behaviors they perceive as usual, particularly when faced with uncertainty. Young individuals are particularly prone to this tendency, as they are more influenced by peer pressure and cultural norms when making decisions or passing judgment. This perspective is supported by recent research by Knoll et al. (2020), which highlights the significant impact of peer behavior and perceived social norms on adolescents, demonstrating how these factors can shape their decisions and behaviors even in the absence of explicit guidance or authority. Relatively, Noori et al. (2023) agreed on the notion that in order to establish their identities and get approval from their peers, young people imitate content trends and parents even stated that their children started using words, gestures, or facial expressions they saw in influencers or online videos, resulting in behavioral changes that go against cultural or familial norms. In addition, Nesi, Telzer, and Prinstein (2021) asserted that juvenile social media use is strongly associated with peer pressure and behavioral conformity. The study also found that social media platforms reinforce particular behaviors through visibility and validation mechanisms such as likes and shares. In support of the notion that digital settings influence offline actions, the researchers discovered that teenagers frequently imitate peers and on-

line role models who seem to be socially rewarded. When damaging challenges, improper language, or skewed societal standards are included in the copied information, this was very troubling.

3.1.2. Lack of self-awareness and avoidance of reality—The growing use of digital media and internet platforms has profoundly altered the way that children, particularly those in elementary school, develop. Concerns have been raised about the potential consequences of early exposure to social media, video-sharing websites, and other internet-based environments on children’s cognitive and emotional development. Among the most urgent concerns are the lack of self-awareness among elementary-aged children and their propensity to evade reality when using these internet platforms. That young children’s perceptions of themselves and their experiences in the real world may be distorted by the rapid intake of carefully chosen content, which is often focused on romanticized portrayals of relationships, lifestyles, and self-representation. Although each participant had different experiences, they shared a common idea for this part. Firstly, parent three was dealing with her elementary child’s obsession with self in terms of social media likes, particularly on Facebook. This type of media enables multiple users to access global information, events, and even track the whereabouts of other account users. In terms of interactions, getting validation depends on how many likes or reactions a certain public displayed posts obtain. In which the parents specified that after every class, after-class hour, or on weekdays, their respective children are prone to checking phones from time to time and conscious of what they see online. This concept is theoretically supported by Pang’s (2022) work, which highlights how early excessive exposure to online settings shifts children’s perceptions, making them more susceptible to escapism, idealism, and misinformation. Some parents described how their kids misinterpreted

the permanence and public nature of their digital footprints, or how they preferred screen time to face-to-face conversations. Likewise, Kolhar et al. (2021) found that students’ non-academic use of social media causes them to become disengaged from their studies and perform worse in class. This pattern was mirrored in the experiences of many of the study’s parents. Moreover, parent 8 shared that her elementary child was overly conscious of her appearance due to the influence of watching video tutorials. There is a positive aspect to allowing the young generation to learn on their own in their own space, utilizing online tutorials like those on YouTube, which feature a variety of instructions uploaded daily. However, the downside was that children are too fragile for mature content. It means not all videos were appropriate for them, who strictly need some guidance. Some proponents, such as those found in the work of Grealish et al. (2020), have pointed out that sharing self-representational content frequently can encourage narcissistic tendencies in young users, thereby strengthening the developmental influence of imitation. In terms of age, Lin and Lachman (2020) also confirmed that age mitigated the relationship between daily social media use and negative impacts, with younger people suffering more severe negative effects when they used social media more frequently. There were fewer negative impacts on older people on the days when they utilized social media more. On the contrary, parent 4 witnessed how his child struggled with a moral dilemma that led to emotional distress at an early age. It was said that the group chat led his child to participate in making fun of other students at school. However, his son was included without being part of it, but he does not know how to respond to the situation. His son was struggling to distinguish right from wrong. It is futile to keep young learners in a community that only shares insults, criticisms, and other intentional prejudices, as it is not an age-appropriate space for them. Several

online communities had publicly showcased an unfriendly atmosphere. In the same way, parent 10 attested when her child was emotionally affected just because of the hateful comment thread of other online users. This parental viewpoint emphasizes how emotionally draining it is to deal with the fallout from online animosity, especially when it directly impacts a young and vulnerable family member. Such experiences demonstrate how online settings, despite their apparent external nature, can profoundly penetrate family life and change parent-child dynamics, highlighting the confluence between digital interactions and offline mental health. These live experiences are consistent with the assertion of Pal (2023) in which each individual's perception varies throughout their lives. While some people were delighted, others felt lonely and isolated, among other undesirable emotions. Everyone must make choices and adjust their lives to meet their environment and circumstances in order to maintain their well-being and quality of life.

3.1.3. Conceal danger on social media sites—However, social media sites are frequently thought of as resources for amusement, self-expression, and connection; a growing corpus of research exposes many hidden risks that disproportionately impact young users. Algorithmic designs that promote excessive use, expose children to inappropriate content, and enable unsupervised contact with strangers are often hidden beneath their visually appealing interfaces. Children in elementary school, who are still learning how to control their emotions and think critically, should be especially concerned about these concerns. These platforms' immersive qualities have the potential to interfere with sleep cycles, reduce family time, and create opportunities for negative experiences, including cyberbullying, online fraud, and digital abuse.

A recurring pattern in participant accounts is the deep worry about the risks associated

with young children's usage of social media, risks that are frequently overlooked until behavioral abnormalities manifest. Parent 5 and 7 expressed their concern after seeing that their child's screen time was progressively undermining important facets of everyday life, such as regular sleep patterns, participation in family events, and attention to face-to-face interactions, specifically in schoolwork. Our minds easily deteriorate when our focus is on the screen for an extended period. The rest of the daily routine will fall apart if that happens continuously. These findings align with the concerns presented by Abi-Jaoude (2020), who emphasized that social media harms children's self-perception and interpersonal relationships, potentially leading to sleep disturbances and emotional dysregulation. Similarly, Agostiniani et al. (2022) described the psychosomatic effects of regular social media use on young people, such as headaches, sleep problems, and eye strain, which are also supported by their personal experiences. Parental testimonials revealed such results, indicating that extended device use had caused their children to become physically and mentally exhausted. Consequently, parent 7 and 9 were terrified upon learning that their child had been interacting with strangers on the internet, some of whom had tried to coerce the youngster into disclosing private information and even making illicit financial transactions that led to scamming and even corrupting young minds. Indeed, alarming and persistently occurring that somehow left unsolved. These narratives demonstrate the negative effects of early and unsupervised social media use on children's cognitive and emotional development, as well as the strain on parent-child relationships and exposure to hazardous or misleading digital interactions. In align with this matter, Kang et al. (2022) hinted that teens' perceived privacy hazard leads them to use rigorous privacy management strategies. The ways in which parental mediation tech-

Fig. 3. The Experiences of Elementary Grade-Level School Parents towards their children’s social media usage

niques impact teens’ privacy management techniques vary, nevertheless. Additionally, active mediation encourages children to use their own

discretion when deciding how much private information to divulge.

3.2. *The coping mechanisms of the elementary grade-level school Parents towards their children’s social media usage*—As younger users, especially elementary-aged children, and particularly students from the Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy, continue to integrate social media into their daily lives, parents are facing increasing difficulties in controlling its influence at home. Parents have developed various coping strategies in response to the changing digital environment. These strategies aim to regulate their children’s online behavior, protect their emotional well-being, and maintain a healthy balance between virtual and in-person interac-

tions. Reactive and proactive tactics are frequently combined in these coping mechanisms, which include monitoring online behavior, limiting screen time, having candid conversations about digital safety, and, in certain situations, completely limiting access.

3.2.1. *Daily Time Management*—To mitigate the detrimental effects of prolonged social media use on their young children, parents participating in this study employed structured daily time management as an emerging coping strategy. At home, parents reported creating regular routines that included technology-free zones, planned breaks, and specific hours for screen time. Particularly in the context of fam-

ilies, parent 1 ensured that these tactics were thought to be crucial for encouraging more meaningful offline connections, better sleep patterns, and healthier digital habits. In order to prevent an over-reliance on social media, Parent 8 sought to establish a sense of discipline and digital balance by establishing regular routines. In addition to reflecting a growing parental awareness of the dangers of unfettered access, this proactive approach emphasizes the value of daily time control as a useful and flexible tool in modern digital parenting. The adoption of such coping strategies shows how parents try to restore order to an increasingly disorganized and technologically oriented part of their kids' lives. This is related to the research of Milivojević et al. (2018), in which they emphasized the importance of proactive parental involvement and role modeling. This strategy was supported by the participating parents, who recognized the value of establishing limits and providing an example of responsible technology use. In a similar vein, Abdelmoneium (2023) outlined four essential tactics used by parents: trust-building, amusement, control, and dialogue, which came up with techniques showing how parents attempted to strike a balance between support and discipline. Additionally, according to Ho et al. (2019), parents can utilize mediation strategies as a time-management tool to help their children navigate the digital landscape more effectively. By applying both active and restrictive mediation, parents managed their children's exposure to social media while also teaching them how to engage with it responsibly. Active mediation involves regular discussions with children about the content they encounter, guiding them in critical thinking and evaluating the content. Meanwhile, restrictive mediation involves enforcing time limits and platform restrictions, which help regulate the duration and nature of their online engagement. These forms enabled parents to address the challenges of social media use in a structured and time-conscious manner.

3.2.2. Transparent dialogue and family-oriented activities—Employing open communication and encouraging family-friendly activities to mitigate the prolonged exposure of their young children to social media is another important coping strategy noted by parent participants. Parents emphasized the importance of having open discussions with their children about digital safety, online content, and their emotional responses to what they encounter on various platforms.

In the parent-child connection, parent 2 attested that this open channel of communication was thought to be essential for establishing trust, promoting self-disclosure, and creating a sense of security. As conscious attempts to reestablish their children in shared experiences and real-world relationships, parents planned five concurrent family-friendly activities, including outdoor play, shared meals, and screen-free bonding time. For parent 4, the relational approach to digital parenting is reflected in these tactics, wherein mutual understanding and emotional intimacy act as protective barriers against the damaging or alienating consequences of excessive online use. In addition to facilitating early intervention when problems emerge, parent 3 attested that the emphasis on communication and family participation serves to further solidify the family's position as a child's primary support network for both digital and emotional development. These patterns of conduct align with the outcomes of Ansari et al. (2020), who recommended that the use of the internet needs to be limited, specifically in terms of surfing different websites and apps, to allow for the essence of communication. In relation, positive mental strategies are necessary since children cope with age-appropriate activities. By then, when parents carefully explain the reason for having a time limit on social media, children will gradually understand and adjust to a healthier balance of media usage. Additionally, creating student-friendly apps might be benefi-

cial for their skills and personality development during free time with their families. Through the integration of relational engagement and structured offline interactions, parents can apply such an approach to digital parenting, emphasizing the importance of emotional intimacy, mutual understanding, and strengthening family ties as crucial strategies for managing young children's digital habits. Moreover, Matsuda et al. (2023) posited that engaging in open dialogue serves vital for parents in managing their children's use of social media. Rather than imposing control without discussion, parents are encouraged to foster ongoing conversations that allow their children to express and reflect on their online experiences. Initiating discussions through open-ended questions creates space for children to articulate their digital behaviors and concerns, which strengthens mutual understanding and emotional support. Mayer et al. (2024) also added that weaving in age-appropriate discussions during these dialogues helps reinforce healthy digital habits. These conversations may involve teaching children about online privacy, helping them identify and avoid harmful content, and guiding them to comprehend how digital interactions can influence their mental and emotional well-being.

3.2.3. Child-friendly online community and equipped digital education—As young children are increasingly exposed to the intricacies and dangers of social media, many parents in this study found that access to structured digital education and the promotion of kid-friendly online networks are essential coping strategies. Instead of relying solely on punitive or restrictive tactics, these parents emphasized the importance of creating online spaces that are socially constructive, developmentally appropriate, and inherently protected. By encouraging safer online environments and fundamental digital skills, parents aim to foster resilience, self-reliance, and thoughtful participation in their children's online behavior. This method pri-

oritizes digital readiness as a crucial tactic for overcoming the challenges of early social media use, reflecting a shift away from reactive control and toward proactive empowerment. For parent 6, Parental self-directed and group efforts to control their young children's prolonged social media use are another noteworthy coping strategy identified by this study. In addition to being informed, parents stated that they joined school-parent organizations to collaborate on creating school-based digital safety rules and interventions. Likewise, Parent 10 stated that from outside the classroom, some parents started or joined neighborhood-based parent organizations whose goals included information exchange, trend analysis, and promoting child-friendly internet spaces. Parent 7 emphasized the importance of participating in local digital literacy classes and programs to stay current on new online dangers and enhance their ability to supervise their children's online behavior. While parent 9 found that setting up fake social media profiles was an especially proactive tactic that let them monitor the sites their kids use. Parents were able to foresee potential risks and gain personal insight into online dynamics through this activity, which was presented as a form of digital mindfulness. These group and instructional initiatives represent a changing paradigm of digital parenting, where active participation, empowerment, and well-informed action are valued more highly than passive limitation. This supports the findings of Armansyah and Munastiwi (2021) who stated that the necessity of recognizing the perspectives and attitudes of educators and learners towards enhancing learning instruction with the help of social media will be led to achievable learning goals such as using YouTube for educational purposes. Moreover, such findings align with Tartari et al. (2019) attested that even Facebook might aid for the improvement of young learners' creativity, interpersonal aspects including sense of citizenship, and online etiquettes when it is utilized

Fig. 4. The Coping Mechanisms of Elementary grade-level school parents towards their children’s social media usage

as a form of educational tool. Also, the use of those platforms will influence student’s learning performances in a virtual manner particularly on how they apply and interact with these social media sites. Ultimately, Barnes and Potter (2021) advocated for the idea that fostering digital literacy in children serves as an effective way for parents to manage their children’s engagement with social media. By equipping their children with the knowledge and skills needed to be present in the digital world, parents empower

them to make responsible choices online. This includes helping children understand the long-term consequences of their digital footprint and the significance of safeguarding personal information in online spaces. When children become digitally literate, they are more capable of identifying online threats and digital interactions with greater awareness, which in turn alleviates some of the burden parents face in constantly monitoring social media use.

3.3. The Insights of Elementary grade-level school Parents towards their children’s social media usage —This study’s elementary parents’ perspectives provide a detailed knowledge of the evolving digital environment their kids are currently living in. Parents have

noticed the phenomenon of early website acquisition as social media becomes more accessible to younger users. This is when children as young as six or seven years old are already creating or using social media accounts, frequently without fully understanding the risks

and responsibilities involved. This rapid uptake has raised concerns about whether today's digital platforms are suitable for kids, and many parents are calling for the creation of more robust, kid-specific online environments that put an emphasis on age-appropriate design, safety, and content control. At the same time, parents stressed the significance of implementing a technologically aware parenting strategy, which incorporates open communication, active monitoring, digital literacy, and new technology experience. A balanced strategy that promotes both digital competency and responsible behavior is what many parents aim to teach their kids instead than just restricting them. These observations demonstrate how parents' roles as proactive contributors to creating a safer and healthier online environment for their kids are growing beyond their traditional role as protectors.

3.3.1. Early website acquisition for younger ages—Concerns among parents about their children's early access to and use of social media platforms during their formative years are being highlighted by information obtained from elementary school parents. Numerous parents observed that their children were increasingly demanding access to or investigating websites and social media apps at progressively younger ages—often before they had developed the emotional maturity or critical thinking skills required to navigate such digital environments safely. Parents are concerned about premature identity formation through digital involvement, exposure to unsuitable content, and online manipulation, which has prompted them to express anxiety over this trend of early website ownership. Parent 3 responded that digital education should start early because they think that elementary school is the best time to teach children the fundamentals of online safety, privacy, and good behavior. Parent 10 further emphasized the importance of early discussions regarding digital safety, stating that it is crucial to have

timely conversations about online activity, cyber threats, and the potential digital consequences. Repeatedly, parent four was convinced that the usefulness of communication as a tool for assisting students with their digital participation is an effective solution to apply. Establishing open channels of communication, according to parents, builds trust and encourages kids to share their internet experiences and ask for help. Parent 1 further emphasized the importance of teaching values and useful skills—such as empathy, critical thinking, and content discernment—through digital exposure. Last but not least, parent 8 understood the importance of setting a positive example for their kids by using media responsibly. Children frequently imitate the digital behaviors they see in adults, they said, which emphasizes the need for parents to model responsible, considerate, and balanced online conduct. This bolsters the findings of Guerrero and Forment (2019), who noted that children as young as five are now extensively using digital platforms, presenting both increased risk exposure and educational potential. The present study highlights concerns about children's early exposure to content that is not suitable for their age group and validates this early engagement through parental narratives. In a similar vein, Agostiniani et al. (2022) and Giumetti and Kowalski (2022) argued that although early participation may foster digital literacy, it also exposes young users to improper information, sexting, and cyberbullying (Awaliyah, Hartati, Tursiva, 2021). Young users' developmental immaturity, which often leaves them without the cognitive skills necessary to navigate such spaces properly, exacerbates these hazards even further (Pang, 2022). When considered as a whole, these results underscore the necessity for a comprehensive parenting strategy that begins with early digital education, continues with open and honest communication, and is reinforced by value-based guidance and positive role modeling. Due to elementary-aged

children's early social media use, families and educational institutions have an even greater obligation to promote responsible digital citizenship from an early age.

3.3.2. A strong and protected online community platform for children—In light of the growing prevalence of digital interaction among elementary-aged users, parents have expressed the pressing necessity for the creation of robust and secure online platforms designed with children in mind. They recommend that these platforms include enhanced privacy settings, robust content control systems, and interactive elements that minimize exposure to hazardous content and online risks while promoting learning and developmentally appropriate experiences. Instead of completely prohibiting digital interaction, these parents support a safer digital environment where kids can interact, learn, and explore in supervised and secure settings. In an increasingly interconnected world, their perspectives contribute to ongoing conversations about the ethics of digital design and the importance of creating safe, inclusive environments that support children's rights and welfare. The need for a learner-centered cyberspace where children can "fit in" appropriately—that is, a digital environment tailored to their social, emotional, and cognitive development—was one of the most prevalent ideas shared by Parent 2. To protect children from unsuitable content, cyberbullying, and exploitation, parents emphasized the importance of robust privacy safeguards, effective content filters, and real-time moderation. Furthermore, parent 9 envisioned a secure online environment where one could not only be protected but also foster friendships, values, and talents. Parents recognized that, when purposefully designed, online platforms might foster healthy peer interactions, improve communication skills, and promote value formation in addition to being viewed through the perspective of risk prevention. Owing to these parental observations, the focus should be on creating secure,

empowering, and developmentally suitable digital places rather than restricting children's access. Each finding reinforces Ansari et al.'s (2020) suggestion to develop student-specific apps that offer content moderation and parental controls, along with educational, skill-building, and safe social interactions. Having a different area that could divert their kids' screen time toward safer online interactions was endorsed by parents. Consequently, Kang et al. (2022) provided evidence in support of the idea that active parental mediation can reduce risks by helping children determine whether the material they post online is suitable. Children must, nevertheless, negotiate unsupervised cyberspaces in the absence of established platforms. Furthermore, Agha et al. (2024) also emphasized the importance of cultivating a safe and child-friendly online space, highlighting that one effective approach is through the integration of online safety nudges—subtle cues that influence behavior without limiting personal freedom. These prompts act as protective tools, helping minimize children's exposure to digital risks while preserving their ability to explore and engage independently. When these safety features are co-developed with the input of young users, they become more meaningful, respectful, and contextually grounded in children's actual online experiences.

3.3.3. Digitally Smart Parenting—The concept of "digitally smart parenting" emerged in the digital age, as parents in elementary school reevaluated conventional parenting techniques in response to the rapid integration of social media into their children's daily lives. This method emphasizes striking a balance between responsible use and access to technology, reflecting a proactive and knowledgeable approach to controlling children's digital involvement. In addition to being aware of the advantages and disadvantages of online platforms, parents who adopt digitally wise practices also implement strategies that promote electronic lit-

Fig. 5. The Insights shared by the parents of the Elementary grade level Students ' Attitudes towards Social Media Usage

eracy, safety awareness, and open communication in the home. Thus, the concept of "digitally smart parenting" becomes essential for helping kids use social media securely and purposefully throughout their early years.

One of the main points of view expressed by Parent 9 was the importance of teaching children how to use technology wisely and ethically. This entails promoting polite online interactions, educating digital etiquette, and fostering critical thinking about online content. Implementing child protection regulations to prevent exposure to adult content was another noteworthy realization. To ensure age-appropriate experiences for young users, parents pushed for stricter regulatory frameworks and platform-based safety measures. Furthermore, parent 5 recognized the necessity of maintaining a balanced approach to social media use, supporting routines that promote screen time regulation and prioritize offline connections, such as academic focus, family bonding, and physical activity. These findings agree with the tactics suggested by Kim and Lou (2019), in which active and restrictive mediation, limiting children's exposure to negative material, and assisting them with digital

interactions can lessen their susceptibility to addiction, emotional discomfort, and cyberbullying. This was also agreed upon by Helfrich et al. (2020), who stated that parental supervision and open communication are critical in mitigating cyber threats. Providing real-world examples and even social involvement can improve family ties and foster emotional control. Mostly, Milivojević et al. (2018) emphasized that parents need to constantly learn and adjust in order to be successful digital role models. Acquiring digitally smart parenting is about giving kids the knowledge, beliefs, and support networks they need to interact with technology in a safe and meaningful way, rather than trying to eradicate it. Taken jointly, these observations support the idea that active, values-based, and preventative methods of regulating kids' internet activity are all part of Digitally Smart Parenting. It integrates regulation, education, and protection to guarantee that kids' digital experiences support their cognitive and emotional development. These parenting techniques are crucial pillars for raising a generation of young media users who are safer and more conscientious as digital environments continue to change.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, an overall and detailed perspective of the study is presented. The summarized findings from the previous chapters were recognized in the implications and future directions. My research aimed to determine the experiences, coping strategies, and insights of parents of elementary-grade-level school students from the Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy concerning social media usage. The qualitative phenomenological research method was employed in this study to achieve my research objectives, and the thematic analysis was applied for data analysis. In this study, I comprehensively investigate the struggles experienced by the parents of elementary students. With the help of these parents, their valuable insights into children's exposure to social media provide an excellent key to the success of this study.

4.1. Implications—Upon thorough investigation, the thematic analysis revealed the following findings from the participants' responses and their corresponding themes, namely: the experiences of parents of elementary grade-level students towards the social media usage were, firstly, the consequences through imitation led young students to adopt online influences regardless of the content shown on the screen. Secondly, the lack of self-awareness and avoidance of reality, along with the concealment of danger on social media sites, held an alarming attitude towards each parent towards their elementary children. Despite these adversities, the parents' coping mechanisms include daily time management, a common yet effective strategy when applied properly. Aside from that, a transparent dialogue, family-oriented activities, a child-friendly online community, and equipped digital education are great strategic avenues to enhance and address the dangers beyond cyberspace. Moreover, this will provide further improvement for both educators and parents to develop online instructions that are inclusive of young individuals. Moreover, their insights regarding the harm on online platforms prompted parents and teachers to recognize the importance of early website acquisition in young children, which could help create an educational and friendly online environment for elementary students. Similarly, a plan for a strong and protected online community plat-

form for children will shield them from excessive information throughout their continued use of online platforms. Primarily, digitally smart parenting was evident in its ability to guide students to be mindful and ethical users of technology, as well as raise awareness of online threats. Nonetheless, we highly emphasize the need for child-focused instruction to address the common cases of online hidden dangers.

Moreover, the results of this study align closely with the fundamental theories of TPACK (Mishra Koehler, 2006), the Theory of Informational Social Influence (Cialdini, 1993), and the Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development (Vygotsky, 1978). Recent studies support these theoretical linkages. In particular, Chai et al. (2020) highlighted the ongoing value of TPACK in helping teachers incorporate technology into their teaching methods, particularly in learning environments mediated by technology. Cialdini's concept of informational social influence was also supported by Knoll et al. (2020), who demonstrated how perceived social norms particularly influence adolescents' decision-making. Daniels (2021) also emphasized the importance of Vygotsky's sociocultural theory in understanding how social interaction mediates cognitive growth, especially in digital and collaborative learning environments. Mishra and Koehler's TPACK emphasizes that each component—namely, pedagogical knowledge (PK), Content Knowledge (CK), and tech-

nological knowledge —has a significant impact on effectively facilitating technology-based instruction, regardless of the setup, whether at school, home, or online. This principle is reflected in the study's results, which highlight the roles of teachers, educational sectors, and parents in terms of virtual platforms. The gathered outcomes show that parents suggested using social media as an educational tool for their children to learn, communicate, enhance creative skills, and interact with other kids, which is exclusive to kids. They also mentioned that it must be a safe and friendly cyber arena to raise awareness about the concept of advancement and online dangers. This supports the view of TPACK that better learning must be continually improved and appropriately recognized. In connection, Cialdini's theory of informational social influence regards the idea of imitation as a positive outlook to consider, as several parents have attested that most of their children have tendencies to copy content they see online. Instead, imitative skills should serve as a great reinforcement to teach elementary students good behavior and social etiquette, both in real-time and virtual communication. Additionally, the study found that most parents believe that engaging in family activities and maintaining a balance between work and family time are beneficial practices, as they instill a learning attitude in their children. Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory of Cognitive Development was also evident in the study findings, in which several parents revealed that their role is crucial in monitoring the digital time of their young kids through participating in family bonding tasks, constant observation of kids' social media attitude, and taking part in school community programs for such issues. According to this theory, learning and development occur most efficiently in the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), provided that more experienced individuals, such as parents, offer sufficient scaffolding or learning guidance during the process.

However, contrary ideas evolved amidst these theoretical alignments. Each theories elaborate on the role of parental guidance. The study found that the gap lies between creating a child-friendly online community and equipping digital education, and a strong and protected online community platform for children. Recently, online threats have become increasingly prevalent, leading to public disputes and harmful incidents. This hinders the effectiveness of the study, as numerous known digital seminars exist, yet the action is still not applied effectively. In general, the study's results emphasized the vital roles of theoretical lenses, namely TPACK, the theory of Informational Social Influence, and the socio-cultural theory of cognitive development, to the parents' adaptive and guiding attitude towards their children's social media usage, as well as on the academic aspect. The study also elaborated these theories by illustrating how parents faced the changes of their elementary kids, handling the situation properly, and reinforcing it with good conduct both in real time and online usage. Mostly, encouraging an online community where every kid is welcome without discouraging the application of the platforms.

4.2. Future Directions—The findings of the parents' examination of their elementary grade children on using online platforms, particularly from the Immaculate Heart of Mary Academy, provided valuable and changeable insights for parents, educators, and school sectors. One significant struggle found is the consequences through imitation in which any social influences can lead to behavioral changes. To address this, the school must demonstrate a focus-oriented personality development from a young age. This will help them have awareness of what is right or wrong in terms of dealing with content not suitable for their age. Thus, this must be incorporated with technological enhancement, such as creating an online group where every child in need is welcome, as suggested by selected parents in the study. Lack

of self-awareness and avoidance of reality also emerged as a recurring struggle. Parents, along with school personnel, must reinforce to get the proper attention of students on their learning in a face-to-face contact because being focused online is not a choice but another technique to make it a better space for learning instead of a hindrance for them to grow. They must reevaluate the necessities of students in using online platforms. In order to further validate and generalize the themes found in this study, future researchers are recommended to use mixed-method or quantitative approaches, especially when it comes to parental coping mechanisms and children's digital habits. The effects of social media use on primary school students over time, particularly to their social development, academic achievement, and emotional resilience, can also be investigated using longitudinal research methodologies. Furthermore, comparative research examining the experiences of parents in urban and rural areas may provide valuable insights into how socioeconomic and contextual factors influence digital parenting. Using morally good, child-centered approaches, incorporating elementary school students' viewpoints could also enhance our understanding of how kids themselves use, interact with, and are affected by social media. Ultimately, future research may focus on developing and evaluating intervention programs that enhance parents' digital literacy and promote children's responsible use of technology. It is recommended that educational institutions incorporate instruction on digital literacy into their curricula for both parents and students. This can be achieved by offering workshops, classroom modules, and community outreach initiatives that emphasize digital safety and responsible online behavior. Age-appropriate legislative frameworks that mandate social media companies to implement built-in safeguards for children, such as content screening, screen-time reminders, and more robust data privacy measures, should be considered by policymakers. It is strongly encouraged that parents stay up-to-date on the latest digital trends, communicate with their kids in an open and judgment-free manner about their online behavior, and set age-appropriate, mutually trusting, and guiding digital boundaries.

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